

**From variants to voltage: channeling MAVEs to tackle disease
Season 2 Episode 2 Transcript**

The Team: Alex Nguyen Ba, Adrine de Souza, Moez Dawood, Kortni Kindree, Katie Partington, Ziyi Dai, and Jerome Freudenberg
Facilitated by the Altas of Variant Effect Alliance

Season 2 Episode 2 Transcript

00;00;00;00 - 00;00;30;10

Alex Nguyen Ba: I remember when I was doing my undergraduate degree, walking late into a classroom for a course that I thought was biology, and seeing on the PowerPoint projector a series of equations. We were then introduced to a set of mathematical models that related to different physical and chemical concepts. I seriously wondered if I had the wrong room. But what is biology, but an integrative field of many disciplines?

00;00;30;12 - 00;01;02;04

In the past episodes of this podcast, we discussed how biology is deeply interconnected with technology, with society, and with computer science. Today, we'll dive into the world of biophysics and try to explore why, with an understanding of physical techniques, we can better understand ourselves. Our body is surrounded by topics from your physics class. The science of biomechanics can allow you to understand why you get shin splints if you don't properly recover after exercise.

00;01;02;06 - 00;01;27;02

The field of fluid dynamics can help you appreciate aspects that relate to atherosclerosis or the cause of sickle cell disease, as we've seen in a previous episode. Optics will give you a better perspective of how your eyes work. And finally, electrical physics is one of the frameworks to study neurons and how axon potentials are triggered. And so, what does this have to do with our podcast?

00;01;27;04 - 00;01;51;21

Well, our cells obey physical laws. And today we'll see what this means. In school, most of us learned what makes a cell: the nucleus, the cytoplasm, and the membrane. And we were taught that the magic happens in the core, the DNA, and that cellular division all starts there. The cytoplasm is the second most remembered part of the cell where all organelles and protein production happens.

00;01;51;23 - 00;02;17;11

But what about the membrane? Think of your skin. It's the biggest organ by area of the body. It's responsible for keeping things in and out, but it's also through the skin that the outside world

interacts with us. When we get an outside signal, like a cold breeze on our skin, the cells in the derm have to pass along the message that we need thermal protection.

00;02;17;13 - 00;02;52;04

How does that work? Which macromolecules receive and transmit this vital information to the rest of the body? Well, the answer is in the membrane. Today we'll learn about membrane proteins, their role in disease, and how MAVE technology can allow for mechanistic understanding of physiological systems.

[Intro music plays]

00;02;52;06 - 00;03;23;05

Welcome back to The VUS Podcast, a series initiated by the outreach efforts of the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance. I'm Alex, a professor at the University of Toronto. And today, the team, Jerome, Ziyi, Katie, Adrine, Moez, Kortni, and I will walk you through a scientific journey to deciphering heart and brain diseases, using electrodes on cells.

Adrine de Souza: Hi, I'm Adrine.

Ziyi Dai: And I'm Ziyi, and I'm so excited to learn more about the research being done on membrane proteins and how that can help us tackle disease.

00;03;23;07 - 00;03;48;11

This class of proteins includes ion channels, small molecule transporters, and signal receptors, all of which connect the cell's internal environment with the outside world.

Adrine: So, what type of diseases can membrane proteins be involved in?

Ziyi: Well, membrane proteins are responsible for many cellular functions. So if they break, that can cause disease in tons of different parts of the body.

00;03;48;13 - 00;04;21;17

It can mean disease ranging from cystic fibrosis to cardiac arrhythmia or even cancer.

Adrine: That sounds really important. I can't wait to hear more about it.

Ziyi: And just to get you even more excited, we're also going to learn about exciting new technologies, enabling more detailed study of these proteins and the potential that unlocks for developing therapeutics.

Adrine: Now, let's introduce you to the first of two amazing researchers working on expanding our knowledge on channel proteins and heart disease.

00;04;21;19 - 00;04;51;26

Welcome, Dr. Andrew Glazer to the VUS podcast.

Andrew Glazer: I'm Andrew Glazer and I am an assistant professor at Vanderbilt University Medical Center.

Adrine: Can you tell us how you got involved with functional genetics and the study of membrane proteins?

Andrew Glazer: Yeah, so I started a postdoc here at Vanderbilt in studying the genetics of arrhythmias. And, you know, pretty early on, I was sitting in these meetings where we had cardiologists who were talking about their patients.

00;04;51;28 - 00;05;13;13

So maybe the patient themselves had an arrhythmia or maybe there was a family member, brother, or a mother who had a sudden death incident and kind of really trying to figure out what was going on. So these patients would get sequenced and a lot of times they would find a variant and they wouldn't know whether the variant was the cause of the disease, maybe the variant had never even been seen before.

00;05;13;15 - 00;05;37;12

So I really started thinking about this clinical question of: how do we best figure out which mutations actually cause disease or not? And then I started reading some papers and hearing some talks at conferences for some pioneering folks who are doing these multiplex assays of variant effect, or MAVE experiments, and at the time a lot of the initial work was being done on cancer genes.

00;05;37;14 - 00;06;14;23

And I just thought it was really groundbreaking, this idea that you could make all the mutations in a gene and study them all together in a single experiment and learn so much about all the variants together. And I thought, you know, that's really what we need for these arrhythmia syndromes. So I started some collaborations with some of those folks and do some of the work to adopt some of the methods from that early work towards studying some of these ion channels in the heart that were linked to arrhythmias.

Adrine: And why are membrane proteins or more specifically, ion channels, of special interest in heart disease?

00;06;14;24 - 00;06;40;05

Andrew Glazer: Yeah, sure. So, I would say there's probably 4 or 5 tier one arrhythmia genes, there's a long tail of different ion channels in the heart. And the normal function of these genes is basically to make channels--so these are membrane proteins, they sit in the cell surface and they pass sodium or potassium or calcium in or out of the cell

00;06;40;07 - 00;06;59;28

and that actually generates the electrical activity of the heart. And what happens is, if you have a mutation that disrupts one of these channels, then you can get bad electrical signaling in your heart that can, in some cases, even lead to a fatal arrhythmia, where your heart kind of goes into a fatal rhythm

00;06;59;28 - 00;07;18;20

and that, if that's not resuscitated, then you can die from it. You know, there's been a lot of work before us figuring out some of the main genes that were involved in arrhythmias and a lot of them turned out to be these ion channels, a couple of different potassium channels, a calcium channel, and so forth.

00;07;18;22 - 00;07;46;18

Adrine: So these channels are basically tunnels inside the cell membranes that allow the exchange of electrical charge particles that will lead to a cascade of electrical signals vital for function. But are they only important in the heart?

Andrew Glazer: Yeah. So there's actually a really broad set of ion channels in our bodies. The last time I looked, there's probably about a hundred different ion channel genes that are linked to rare genetic disorders.

00;07;46;18 - 00;08;07;26

And so, it's a really interesting class of protein. You know, a lot of these are in the heart, that can cause arrhythmias when you have mutations. But you also have some in the brain, that can cause, either seasonal disorders or other neurodevelopmental defects. There's channels kind of all over. So there's channels involved in sensations, a sensation of temperature, pressure.

00;08;07;27 - 00;08;27;20

There's channels involved in other organs. There's even channels involved in kidney function and bone function and all sorts of things. So I think it's a really interesting class of protein. How do you get a protein to fold, to make a channel that has as ions flowing through it? And you don't just want to turn these channels on all the time

00;08;27;23 - 00;08;51;19

in a lot of cases. So a lot of cases, you need to have kind of complex regulation of the channels where they're going to only open for a brief time, and then maybe they'll close or they'll open under certain conditions, under a certain stimulus. But each ion channel is its own special gene, where we have to figure out exactly how it's activated and how it's turned off and really learn about the specialized biology of these individual genes.

00;08;51;21 - 00;09;08;05

Ziyi: So, ion channels are involved in every organ and need a complicated regulatory system to keep them open for the right amount of time and in the right conditions. And if that breaks in any way, that can result in tons of different diseases.

00;09;08;08 - 00;09;38;02

Adrine: That sounds incredibly complicated. I'm starting to understand why it's so hard to figure out how ion channels work and the consequences of their malfunctioning. I'd love to hear some examples about how we can start to untangle some of this work in practice. Andrew, you've done

specific work with the ion channels SCN5A and KCNE1, I'd be interested to hear about what you discovered there.

00;09;38;04 - 00;09;56;11

Andrew Glazer: Yeah, so SCN5A is a sodium channel in the heart and it actually kickstarts the electrical signaling in the heart, so it kickstarts the action potential. So sodium flowing into the cell through SCN5A, that's the first major piece of the action potential.

00;09;56;12 - 00;10;16;17

It opens just for a few milliseconds, a brief spurt of sodium comes in, and then it closes or inactivates. Yeah, one of the really interesting things about SCN5A is that there's four different transmembrane domains that come together to form the final channel. And when we started out, we didn't really know where the disease-causing mutations were,

00;10;16;19 - 00;10;42;14

and one of the things we're learning is that the loss-of-function mutations are spread throughout the channel. So in all of these different transmembrane domains, a single one out of the 2000 amino acids, you can tweak it a little bit in one of these really important regions, and it causes total loss of function of the protein. And by contrast, the gain-of-function mutations, are not really spread out,

00;10;42;14 - 00;11;06;28

they're kind of specifically localized to a few really interesting hotspot locations. And it kind of makes sense if you think about the mechanism. So essentially, the channel opens and then pretty quickly inactivates. And the way that works is that there's a piece of the protein that swings shut. And the old model is that it actually physically blocks the pore, blocks the place where the sodium comes through.

00;11;07;05 - 00;11;29;01

The new model is that it binds near where the pore is and causes conformational changes. So we're still trying to come up with the best metaphor we can use to kind of describe that process. And so if you have mutations in one of these specific regions of the protein that's responsible for closing the protein or inactivating the protein, then you can get a gain-of-function mutation.

00;11;29;04 - 00;11;52;25

So we really see some interesting specific positions in the protein that are linked to this inactivation process, that can cause gain of function when you have a mutation in them.

Adrine: What about KCNE1? What did you learn from that one?

Andrew Glazer: Yeah. KCNE1 is actually the first gene that we completed a full mutational map for,

00;11;52;25 - 00;12;12;01

so I'm very proud of that. And one of the reasons for that is it's actually the smallest arrhythmia gene. So it was kind of easiest for us to complete. And just on a practical level, it was really useful for us to do the KCNE1 map, because we learned a lot of little technical details about: how to do these types of experiments?

00;12;12;03 - 00;12;30;10

How do we make a mutant library? How do we get it into cells? How do we do some of these assays? How do we do the sequencing and visualization? And so that's really helped us as we've expanded to some of the other larger genes and we use our lessons from this small KCNE1 gene to do the experiments for the larger gene.

00;12;30;13 - 00;12;53;22

But we've also learned a lot of really interesting biology about how KCNE1 works. So KCNE1 is part of a broader complex of a couple different proteins that form a potassium channel. And from our maps, it really looks like a lot of the mutations that alter the function of the channel are specifically disrupting the interactions with some of these other proteins.

00;12;53;25 - 00;13;16;06

And so that was really interesting to learn about. And there were also a lot of really specific surprises or specific positions in the protein that have to, for example, get glycosylated, that seem to be important. And there was also this really interesting finding about nonsense variants. So it turns out, you can actually chop off about half of the protein, the second half of the protein,

00;13;16;11 - 00;13;35;07

and you can get a KCNE1 protein that still makes it to the right place, still goes to the membrane, and in some cases, even still works. So that was kind of a pretty surprising result for us. And in terms of the clinical translation, our KCNE1 scores actually do a pretty good job.

00;13;35;07 - 00;13;58;08

They're not perfect, but they do nearly perfectly correlate with the known biology about which mutations are pathogenic or benign. So we think that our scores could be used going forward in the clinic as well.

Ziyi: Wow, the part about the nonsense variant is really interesting. Those mutations stop the protein from being fully built, so we expect them to be really damaging.

00;13;58;11 - 00;14;21;11

The fact that some of them still work is really surprising.

Adrine: Have you thought more about the nonsense pattern? Is this a more systematic pattern, or do you think it's a unique feature of this gene?

Andrew Glazer: Yeah, I think KCNE1 itself doesn't make a full channel. So its main function is to bind to other channel proteins and activate them.

00;14;21;13 - 00;14;43;13

So I think that may kind of explain some of its unique biology in that, for a lot of the other channel proteins, they're really sensitive to nonsense mutations and you chop off half of the protein, you would not get a functioning channel at all. But because KCNE1's main role is to activate other proteins, all you really need is those domains that bind those other proteins and activate them,

00;14;43;15 - 00;15;12;10

and there's a bigger chunk of the protein that you can remove and have a functional protein.

Adrine: So can we consider the maps for KCNE1 and SCN5A complete? Or is there more to be done?

Andrew Glazer: I think one of the really interesting aspects of these experiments is that setting up a MAVE experiment for a new gene takes a long time and you unfortunately don't see any results till the end.

00;15;12;10 - 00;15;34;26

So there's maybe about ten steps you have to get working and maybe at step nine you start to see data. And so that can be a little frustrating when you're first doing a MAVE. But, you know, maybe it takes a couple years to set up the experiment the first time, but doing the experiment a second time on the same gene, on the same pool of mutants you've already made, maybe with a slightly different assay or a slightly different condition, takes a very little amount of time

00;15;34;28 - 00;16;00;17

and is relatively efficient. So I think one of the big directions for the future is actually multiple contextual maps on the same gene or the same pool of variants. And so you can imagine taking a single protein and measuring variants in lots of different contexts. So maybe different genetic backgrounds or different environmental conditions, changing temperature, adding in different binding partners,

00;16;00;20 - 00;16;28;03

adding in the presence of a drug that modulates the protein, and really generating a whole series of multiple maps for the same gene. And that will actually really give you a lot of interesting detail into the biology of how these variants are working--what's the mechanism through which they're working? And, you know, you can even imagine a precision medicine experiment where, we might have a new drug that interacts with the protein, and we want to know, for patients, which patients might respond to that drug,

00;16;28;03 - 00;16;52;02

so maybe some mutations just don't interact with that drug or don't respond to that drug at all and some mutations do respond. So you could do a MAVE experiment, in the presence and then in the absence of that drug, and see which mutations respond to that molecule. So I think the future is really bright for MAVE experiments and I think it's too early to do one single MAVE experiment on a single gene and declare victory.

00;16;52;04 - 00;17;16;28

I think you want to kind of go back and actually do lots of different contextual experiments on the same protein.

Adrine: So we heard from Andrew how important understanding ion channels is for tackling heart disease and how MAVEs can help us understand how they work. But what about other membrane proteins: can they also help us understand them more generally as well?

00;17;17;01 - 00;17;44;26

Ziyi: And we also heard that even though a lot of MAVEs have been done on different proteins, what we really need is to do deeper experiments on individual proteins to really learn how different mutations work with different drugs and environments.

Adrine: Our other specialist, Dr. Willow Coyote-Maestas, is doing work in exactly these spaces, connecting MAVEs with membrane proteins, molecular biophysics, and multiple contexts.

00;17;44;29 - 00;18;12;19

Let's hear what he has to say.

Willow Coyote-Maestas: Hi. I'm Willow Coyote-Maestas, I am an assistant professor at UCSF in bioengineering and therapeutic sciences.

Ziyi: Can you tell us about how you got your start with MAVEs and membrane proteins?

Willow Coyote-Maestas: So I got started doing mutational scanning in MAVEs largely because in my PhD, I was working on protein engineering and I was creating variant libraries

00;18;12;21 - 00;18;33;12

and developed a lot of the foundational technologies that people use and still use to this day for making domain insertion libraries to engineer new protein features. And as I was going through that, I became far less interested in the protein engineering personally and more interested in how could we use these approaches to learn things about proteins themselves,

00;18;33;12 - 00;18;54;27

the basic science. And Doug Fowler came to University of Minnesota, where I was a graduate student, and gave a talk and introduced me to a lot of the mutational scanning work his lab was

doing and really opened my eyes to that. And then I came as a visitor to UCSF in the last year of my PhD with Jamie Fraser, who had been thinking about deep mutational scanning for quite a while,

00;18;54;29 - 00;19;17;14

and that made me start to think about, oh, I could start making deep mutational scanning libraries, but incorporate the same high-throughput methods I was using for engineering new proteins and learn something about the proteins and connect it directly to human health. And then when I started as a fellow at UCSF, a somewhat independent fellow, I decided to take a broader scope to start working on membrane proteins.

00;19;17;14 - 00;19;41;23

And the reason why we work on membrane proteins is because membrane proteins interact with the environment outside of the cell and they're overrepresented as targets for drugs. And then GPCRs are the overwhelmingly largest targets for drugs. And then small molecule transporters interact with and move drugs into the liver for further metabolism. And in other cases, transporters control physiology.

00;19;41;28 - 00;20;02;05

And so genetic variation in them as well underlies changes in human health and disease. And membrane protein biology from the basic perspective, because technically it's a very challenging field, tends to fall decades behind other protein fields. And so there's a ton of questions to answer and what that means is in a lot of cases, there's a lack of utility.

00;20;02;08 - 00;20;30;26

And the final reason why membrane proteins are really important, or an illustration is, I would argue that the biggest success of precision medicine from a developing therapeutics based on mechanism is CFTR or cystic fibrosis treatment. And that is a case that required knowledge of how this mutation delta 508, which afflicts tens of thousands of people worldwide, how that affected people to be able to guide small molecule screens.

00;20;31;03 - 00;20;51;23

And without that mechanistic knowledge, you couldn't treat disease. And in my mind, that's kind of where the mutational scanning people need to go. Like if we want to move behind just clinical variant interpretation for very rare and simple Mendelian diseases, we need to understand mechanism. So membrane proteins are like an ideal target for that because we don't know much there,

00;20;51;23 - 00;21;20;06

but they're overwhelmingly overrepresented in disease and pharmacology.

Ziyi: I've heard about that drug! So learning more about the mechanism by which a mutation broke the membrane protein CFTR led to this amazing treatment for cystic fibrosis that's saving tens of thousands of lives today.

Adrine: That's really cool. I wonder what other disease membrane proteins are involved in.

Ziyi: Can you talk a little more on the general relevance of membrane proteins in disease?

00;21;20;08 - 00;21;41;03

Willow Coyote-Maestas: So it really depends on which one specifically. So ion channels for instance, which Andrew Glazer I think will be giving a podcast at the same time as this and probably will talk more about ion channels and their association with cardiac disease, there are other ion channels that are associated with neuro-developmental disorders and psychiatric disorders, like schizophrenia, for which we don't have any good treatments.

00;21;41;03 - 00;22;10;26

And you have complex disease there, depression and bipolar disorder and all these things. We've been working on transporters more recently, small molecule transporters that are associated with metabolism. There are about 450 SLC transporters. Of them, around 100 are directly associated with a rare genetic disease and then 400 of the 450 have variants in them that are associated with changes in drug response or common disease.

00;22;11;02 - 00;22;38;00

And so, they're wildly overrepresented in metabolic disorders, like carnitine deficiencies that affect infants. But there are literally thousands of diseases associated with membrane proteins, that are likely afflicting hundreds of millions of people worldwide, for which there's no real mechanistic information for how they're breaking and so how to treat it.

Adrine: Whoa, hundreds of millions of people?

00;22;38;00 - 00;23;20;18

Sounds like we really have to work on understanding membrane proteins better.

Ziyi: But where does molecular biophysics come in? Can we use that to study membrane proteins.

Willow Coyote-Maestas: Yeah. So molecular biophysics is the study of proteins, DNA, RNA, but using approaches from physics, so computational modeling based on physical principles, to understand, at the molecular and atomistic level, how do these proteins actually work? How does DNA interact with proteins? And the fundamental constraints of molecular biophysics historically has been it is incredibly challenging, especially membrane proteins.

00;23;20;21 - 00;23;47;15

Many people will focus their entire career on a single protein or a single family of proteins. In ion channels, there's this part that's called the S4-S5 linker that's in between two transmembranes. And it's really, really important in coupling of voltage to channel opening. Probably 100 to 200 PhDs have been spent making individual mutations of this and doing these really careful, beautiful studies to understand the coupling of these two components

00;23;47;17 - 00;24;15;09

just because the methods are hard.

Adrine: So we look to molecular biophysics to understand how the different parts of a protein work. But doing this is super hard for membrane proteins.

Ziyi: Is there a way that mutational scanning can make this easier?

Willow Coyote-Maestas: Historically, the field has been limited by a lack of data, because the methods have been really challenging. In contrast to like soluble proteins, where it's more organized by like protein dynamics and protein folding.

00;24;15;09 - 00;24;34;20

And you can make 30 to 100 structures or even thousands of structures of a single protein and do that with the same amount of resources that you can maybe solve of a soluble protein, as you can

do with like 1 or 2 structures. Obviously, mutational scanning provides this incredible tool because it doesn't matter if a protein is in the membrane or if it's in the cytosol.

00;24;34;27 - 00;24;56;26

So there's all these opportunities to answer fundamental questions like how do they fold, which has long been an incredibly challenging field. Or how do they function. And we can develop unbiased maps of how they function. So that's really what the paper that we have coming up is on, is using mutational scanning plus cryo-EM to solve structures of proteins

00;24;56;29 - 00;25;17;10

and then using mutational scanning on a GPCR that senses protons, they're involved in pH-sensing around your body, and then trying to uncover what the molecular basis of pH-sensing is in that receptor. Something like that wasn't possible before from an unbiased perspective. And that means like, a lot of times, it's searching in the dark after you get a structure and then trying to make a handful mutations.

00;25;17;14 - 00;25;46;27

It's a hard problem and mutational scanning just makes it so much easier.

Ziyi: To summarize, it's been much easier to use structural biology techniques to study soluble proteins which flow around in the cell than membrane proteins. But mutational scanning provides an approach that's agnostic to the type of protein, because it relies on measuring the impact of genetic variants to determine function, creating new opportunities for studying membrane proteins.

00;25;46;29 - 00;26;09;09

Willow Coyote-Maestas: And then the other opportunity is molecular biophysics has been constrained to being like a pretty basic field. Let's focus on like these incredibly beautiful, but detailed, studies. And that work doesn't always translate to like: why does that matter for physiology? And with mutational scanning, we're doing things in a cell already, we can connect this to clinical genetics.

00;26;09;13 - 00;26;30;08

And so we can take these like beautiful, biophysical models and then inform the genetics and I think solve some of the problems in genetics, while also making biophysics more relevant to the world. And in the world of all these predictive models, what we need is better data that's more refined, and a biophysics lens is what's required to get there.

00;26;30;08 - 00;27;10;09

Ziyi: So mutational scanning not only helps tackle some of the technical challenges in biophysics, but also enables a more direct connection between the field and human health. Can you give us an example of something you learned from this approach?

Willow Coyote-Maestas: One of the general things we've learned is that overwhelmingly, if you look at the effects of, say, 10,000 mutations on these membrane proteins, and then you measure multiple phenotypes like surface expression and the actual function of this protein, we find overwhelmingly loss-of-function variants affect the surface expression or whether you get folding defects.

00;27;10;16 - 00;27;34;09

However, in the cases of the cardiac ion channel that we worked on, Kir2.1, which is under very strong purifying selection, you in fact find most of the clinical variants are affecting the protein activity and not the surface expression, which I find quite interesting and implies that something like VAMP-seq would not work in the case of ion channels.

00;27;34;11 - 00;28;09;18

Adrine: VAMP-seq stands for variant abundance by massively parallel sequencing, which measures how mutations affect how much of a protein is made.

Willow Coyote-Maestas: So overall, we find mutations primarily affect loss of function through folding. But in the case of at least the one protein we've done that's under strong purifying selection, you really need to look at the protein activity itself, which is a deep can of worms to figure out, because that needs to be protein-specific and requires protein-specific knowledge to interpret what is functionally going on.

00;28;09;21 - 00;28;45;21

Adrine: So by measuring different aspects of protein function, like its expression or activity, we get a better understanding of the mechanisms by which mutations affect the protein.

Ziyi: Wow, that sounds really cool, but also really complicated. Are there different strategies for measuring different phenotypes in a protein? Can you do multi-phenotypic mutational scans?

Willow Coyote-Maestas: So multi-phenotypic or multi-parametric mutational scanning is the idea where, as I've been talking about, there are many ways that a mutation can affect a membrane protein or any protein.

00;28;45;23 - 00;29;09;02

And if you don't have ways to delineate how a mutation affects the protein, we are limited in our ability to take the next step, we are limited to develop therapeutics in a precise way or guide the use of therapeutics. And so in the context of our first mutational scan on Kir2.1, we used a measurement for surface expression, using an antibody that bound an epitope

00;29;09;02 - 00;29;37;16

that was extracellularly exposed, and we can fluorescently tag that and sort that. But it's a really hard problem. This is why I started working on transporters and GPCRs more recently. And so in transporters what we've been using is: many transporters, we can use the abundance-based assays that Doug Fowler has developed and Lea Starita, you know, where you just have a fluorescent tag on the protein and you can co-express the rest of fluorescent protein, or you can just tag it with the entire fluorescent protein and use that to measure protein abundance.

00;29;37;19 - 00;29;54;24

And so that has worked reasonably well. But all of these transporters move small molecules across the membrane. And many of these small molecules are chemotherapeutics, which are cytotoxic. And of course, there's a ton of chemotherapeutics. So we can do survival screens for the transporters. Or there's fluorescent substrates that people in the field have been using for a long time.

00;29;54;28 - 00;30;28;08

So in the transporter space, we're mostly using survival-based screens. But more recently, what we've been doing and we're gonna have a paper out that's working on GPCRs using fluorescent readouts for signaling, but a fundamental challenge that has plagued these systems is a lack of dynamic range in these sorts of fluorescent signaling assays. And we've engineered a reporter system, using a number of bells and whistles that I won't get into right now, that allows us to be

able to detect very confidently what basal activity looks like of these receptors, and then how activating it changes

00;30;28;10 - 00;30;48;20

activation. And we've already done, in unpublished work, is be able to do full dose response curves with this. So we can start doing meaningful pharmacology and be able to ask questions like, how do variants change the functional effects of different ligands like opioids, where it's known different variants can tune the response in people to that. And that's kind of where we're going in general.

00;30;48;20 - 00;31;13;17

And where I think the field needs to go is to develop really sensitive assays that are really just copying cell biologists and what cell biologists have been doing for a really long time, and pharmacologists. But finding a way to do it, at scale in pooled screens, because without that, we will struggle to develop precise medicines. But also in say the case of pharmacology, there are a lot of fundamental questions like, what's the molecular basis of efficacy?

00;31;13;17 - 00;31;41;05

Or why do certain ligands work differently than others?

Adrine: I see. So essentially you use lots of different assays on the same protein to target different aspects of its function. And then that tells you something about how a mutation really works. And you can also repeat the assay in different environments, like drug concentrations, to tackle how the effect of the mutation changes in different conditions or contexts.

00;31;41;10 - 00;32;02;20

We have an episode about that.

Ziyi: Seems like an incredible amount of work goes into understanding just a single protein. And this is what we need for mutational scanning to help design therapeutics? I'd love to hear more about how we can get there.

Willow Coyote-Maestas: I haven't touched on too much, yeah, what is the relationship between the expression of a protein and the function?

00;32;02;23 - 00;32;27;09

Because a lot of people are doing these VAMP-seq assays, you know, but we're doing it all in overexpression systems and we don't know how that translates to function. Where this really matters is most variants are heterozygous, especially in proteins that are under constraint, because you don't get two copies of it, right? So if you have one loss-of-function-like variant, say you have a 30% decrease in expression in one of your copies and the other is totally fine, what does that mean in physiology?

00;32;27;12 - 00;32;48;06

And if we can't answer that question, I think we're going to really struggle to make impact clinically. And then on the flip side, drug discovery, people think about this all the time with CFTR, like they know the small molecules don't fully rescue CFTR to 100% of physiological function. And patients, oftentimes still have stomach problems, but not lung problems anymore.

00;32;48;08 - 00;33;14;11

But that's enough for them to go from being totally debilitated and dying in their 20s to living a relatively normal life. But what is the percentage that you need that when you lose a variant, lose physiology? And I think questions like that are really important because there's many of these things that at least without these multi-phenotypic assays and then without knowing how, when we measure expression, how that translates to function, what that means.

00;33;14;14 - 00;33;30;26

And then the final area that I think we're going to struggle with going forward is, as a field, we're focusing on the really, really easy things and where we can make marginal gains and think about all the rare diseases, there's a subset that are going to work for MAVEs, and then maybe if we solve this expression-function stuff, we'll get there.

00;33;30;28 - 00;33;54;08

But what really matters is all the polygenic diseases, you know, the common diseases where you'll have the same genes have mutations that are less deleterious, but that, in combination with other variants or different expression levels. So it's all about these interactions between multiple genes and say, a genetic circuit. And we need to start figuring out how to make perturbations or model multiple perturbations in the context of a physiological system.

00;33;54;10 - 00;34;22;22

I think that that's really where the bigger impact is. Okay, say we start with a transporter that in really rare cases results in a rare disease. And then that same transporter in the context of a couple of other transporters, with drugs involved, inhibits one other transporter. And you have this transporter that has a loss of function variant that's less penetrant, gives rise to a liver disorder that mimics that rare genetic disease.

00;34;22;25 - 00;34;48;06

And then you to look at that same transporter in combination with 30 other genes, you get a condition like fatty liver disease that afflicts like 5% of people during their life. Like building out that way, I think is one way we get to this.

Ziyi: Oh, okay, I see. The multi-parametric scans on a single protein can help with understanding rare diseases that only happen by disrupting that protein,

00;34;48;08 - 00;35;17;07

but most diseases are much more complex and involve disrupted function in many different proteins. So actually, we're going to need to measure all of them at the same time too.

Adrine: And I thought multiple assays of a single protein was already a lot. How far down does the rabbit hole go?

Ziyi: I'd love to hear another example of how targeting the effects of variants on physiology like this can be used to understand disease.

00;35;17;09 - 00;35;43;18

Willow Coyote-Maestas: So I think the example of that, at least in the context of physiology, when we start to think about a more complex system, where we have a defined physiological outcome, where you have a handful of different, say, transporters, enzymes, hormone receptors that are all associated in combination, in the context of drugs with a specific physiological outcome, there's one called drug-induced cholestasis.

00;35;43;21 - 00;36;05;04

And in that case, you have a transporter that moves molecules in that are bile salts, a transporter that moves molecules out that are also bile salts. And you have an enzyme that takes cholesterol and turns it into that. And then you have a hormone receptor that, inside the cell, senses the bile salt and then rebalances the expression of these different proteins.

00;36;05;06 - 00;36;29;18

And then when you have genetic variants in either the hormone receptor or one of the transporters, in the combination of a drug hitting the other transporter over time, you can have the accumulation of too much cholesterol and then you have liver injury. In that case, we struggle to make predictions of like, how much does this variant affect this clinical phenotype in the context of a drug hitting another part?

00;36;29;20 - 00;36;54;00

If we can identify kind of elegant, simple systems like this, we can make predictions of the whole system and then connect that to drug adverse events. Then maybe we can understand a little bit better how these complex interactions give rise to something physiological, which I think will reveal a lot about physiology itself--which is how do those variants affect the biophysics and what does that mean for physiology?

00;36;54;03 - 00;37;26;13

Adrine: That sounds really impactful, I mean, if we can understand a genetic disease to that degree, where if we map what every possible mutation in multiple proteins could do in response to different drugs, that sounds like it would be incredible for developing treatments.

Ziyi: I'm impressed with how far the technologies have come to enable this type of work. I'm curious if there is stuff in the works that could really supercharge these multi-functional screens.

00;37;26;16 - 00;37;49;20

What do you think are the next steps in terms of mutational scanning methods development?

Willow Coyote-Maestas: Phenotypically, we just need more rich assays that allow us, like being able to do dose response with receptors will totally, I think, revolutionize receptor biology at scale. And there's translational reasons for that, which is we struggle to predict the effects of mutations.

00;37;49;23 - 00;38;08;06

There's also translational reasons that we struggle to affect the functional properties of ligands. And we don't have any functional data to understand which residues are interacting functionally with different types of ligands and how does that result in a functional response. Structure-function studies have really struggled with that, because they're mostly on the structure side and not the function side.

00;38;08;06 - 00;38;30;10

So we need a lot of functional data and that could be used to guide the development of therapeutics. In the transporter space, I would love to be able to do the same thing, to be able to have some sort of very sensitive assay. I think that the challenge right now is what we use is a lot of fluorescent readouts, because a lot of the transcriptional readouts saturate really easily and they're very hard to tune.

00;38;30;13 - 00;38;55;14

Whereas with fluorescence, you can see the fluorescence immediately and then you can have a feedback cycle, it's just so fast with it. So I think having a better set of transcriptional readouts that we can read out by sequencing, the effect of, say, signaling, and hooking up signaling to many, many other systems would be revolutionary. I would say, for ion channels, which I have hinted at a number of times that it's really challenging,

00;38;55;16 - 00;39;20;28

I think what we need there is we need something that's time resolved. We are going to struggle to measure the effects of variants that are subtle on something like an action potential. That's what people in clinical genetics, who are taking individual variants and characterizing them, have been doing for a very, very long time and really beautiful work, you know, but they always use patch-clamp electrophysiology, which is incredibly challenging, right?

00;39;21;03 - 00;39;46;27

We probably aren't gonna be able to patch clamp 10,000 variants or whatnot at once. But, if we had an optical readout, that would get us a long way there.

Ziyi: Wait, doesn't Dr. Glazer work on automated patch clamping? Maybe we can ask him for more details.

Adrine: That's right. He's done incredible work on the technological challenges to do large scale effect mapping of these channels.

00;39;46;29 - 00;40;19;26

Dr. Glazer, can you talk a bit about automated patch clamping strategy?

Andrew Glazer: So the classic way that ion channels are measured is a method called patch clamping. And this is a method that's gone back all the way to, I don't know, the 1960s or 70s. And it essentially involves, you sit in a dark room looking under a microscope and you find a cell that you're interested in studying, and then you stab it with a very small pipette, and then you can measure the current through the channels.

00;40;19;28 - 00;40;36;08

You can maybe manipulate the cell in different ways to activate the channels and then you can measure the current that comes through the channels. And so you maybe sit and you do an experiment for 20 minutes, and then you get one cell worth of data, and then you rinse and repeat for eight hours, and then you get maybe a few replicate cells.

00;40;36;10 - 00;40;59;06

So obviously this is not very scalable to all 40,000 variants in a full gene. That's the real gold-standard measurement that you can do on a cell and you can get lots of really precise, detailed information about how much current there is, how the channel opens, how the channel inactivates, how the channel closes, how the channel recovers from the activation, all sorts of detailed parameters that you might be interested in.

00;40;59;08 - 00;41;19;19

So obviously, for the MAVE experiments, we get the scale because we're studying thousands of mutations at once, but we don't really get the precision in terms of all of these detailed measurements about how the channels are working. And so that's why we're basically collapsing the complicated behavior of a 2000 amino acid protein down to a single number.

00;41;19;21 - 00;41;42;28

So we're kind of losing a little bit of the detail of the resolution that you might want. So there's kind of an intermediate level of scale, which is this automated patch clamp experiment. And that's something that we've been working on in the past five years and it's essentially a robot. It's an automated instrument that can, at the same time, use patch clamping on 384 cells at once.

00;41;43;00 - 00;42;07;29

And so what that really enables us to do is get a bit of the scale that you get with a MAVE experiment, where we could actually, in a single experiment, study wild-type cells, but also lots of different mutant cells and get lots of replicates. And the data that we're getting is these precise measurements where we're accurately measuring how much current there is and what voltage the channel opens at and how long does it take to recover from inactivation,

00;42;07;29 - 00;42;30;00

all these really detailed parameters of the channel that you might be interested in. So over the past few years, we and other groups have been working on this method and kind of collectively we've studied at least a thousand variants across a few of the major ion channel genes, so we're starting to get a bit of the scale that we get with the MAVE experiments and we get this kind of detailed resolution.

00;42;30;03 - 00;42;47;15

So ultimately, I think combining different methods, using both the automated patch clamping, as well as the MAVES to really get that big scale. And then, obviously for certain specific variants, you really want to dive in and do a deep study on it to figure out some new interesting mechanism.

00;42;47;18 - 00;43;14;09

And then, traditional manual patch clamping still has its place as well, in terms of really detailed measurements of ion channel function. So I think combining all these different levels of experiments is the way forward.

Adrine: That's awesome. How does that multiplexing work?

Andrew Glazer: We're doing two different types of experiments. So one of them is the automated patch clamping, where we actually generate single mutations and single lines of cells, not actually multiplexing.

00;43;14;09 - 00;43;37;15

So the multiplexing comes at the level of the instrument, which can do 384 wells at a time. And then separately, we're doing other MAVE experiments where we're doing the classic pooled experiments, where we're making pools of mutants, thousands of different mutants, and studying them with high-throughput sequencing based readouts. So for those experiments, we never actually interact with a single mutant one at a time,

00;43;37;15 - 00;44;10;26

we're working on pools. So we're kind of doing both types of experiments.

Adrine: I see. That's really cool, sounds like an interesting machine. Was it developed specifically for this use case?

Andrew Glazer: The machine was actually originally developed to test drugs. So if you imagine you're a pharmaceutical company and you're interested in screening through 40,000 random chemicals to find a novel inhibitor or activator of an ion channel, you might want a 384-well robot to do that.

00;44;10;29 - 00;44;34;12

And you could throw different compounds on the wild-type channel and find which ones activate or inhibit the channel. We and a couple other groups kind of stole that instrument and stole the idea and instead of studying drugs, we're now using it to study mutations. So instead of throwing 40,000 different compounds, we're throwing 400 different mutants on the machine and measuring this function of all the different mutants of the machine.

00;44;34;14 - 00;44;59;20

Ziyi: Wow, sounds creative. I love hearing about things like this, where something originally designed for different use case gets repurposed.

Adrine: We understand the need for contextual maps, but considering that we are not close to having a map for all the 20,000 genes in the genome, how can we align the needs for multiple contexts over maps with the goal of completing all these genes?

00;44;59;22 - 00;45;17;28

Andrew Glazer: If you start doing the math for how many possible mutations are in the genome and how much it costs us to do one of these experiments, at the current level of funding that all of our labs have, I don't think we quite have enough money to do every single mutation in the genome quite yet. You know, we're still obviously applying for more grants to get more funding.

00;45;17;28 - 00;45;41;14

But, I think this idea of shallow mutational scanning where, if you think about, okay, there's a hundred different ion channel genes, maybe after doing a few different ion channel genes, we can actually infer some knowledge about the next channel. And especially a lot of these channels are homologous. So for example, for KCNQ1, we have KCNQ2, KCNQ3, all the way through KCNQ5.

00;45;41;17 - 00;46;04;16

And so maybe once you, for example, do a deep mutational scan of KCNQ1, you don't actually need to do a full deep mutational scan of KCNQ2 through 5, maybe some kind of shallow mutational scanning. Plus, kind of leveraging the knowledge we learned from KCNQ1 either by us humans or maybe even by AI to help predict how the maps would transfer over to the other genes.

00;46;04;18 - 00;46;32;06

Adrine: But the question is, can we or should we trust computational predictors with that responsibility?

Ziyi: Oh, we covered that in the previous episode already?

Adrine: Wshh I know, but I really want to know what Dr. Coyote thinks.

Willow Coyote-Maestas: I think that the variant effect predictors do a terrible job currently in physical chemistry, so they need to get better at that. But say they can like spit out a map that's reasonably accurate for our proteins, right?

00;46;32;06 - 00;46;46;18

And let's say we go ahead and we do this model for all membrane proteins where we can predict the effect on destabilization for all of them. And actually succeed at that, which I don't know if we can, but like, say we do succeed at that part, right? Then we're going to have a subset of variants,

00;46;46;18 - 00;47;09;03

and those like the folding defects are relatively boring, you don't get anything out of that. And, you know, most of the variants don't do anything. And then the largest potential group of the variants, all they do is biogenesis defects. And so there's actually a very small subset of variants that do anything interesting functionally, where it's worthwhile doing all of these multi phenotypic screens to figure out what they're doing.

00;47;09;05 - 00;47;28;25

If we had a better handle a priori of what those are going to be and then if base editors like worked really well, you actually got high sensitivity readouts or perturbations that you could actually read out with these phenotypic assays. And I think that would be so much more elegant and nicer. But we have to, like, build up from the ground to do that.

00;47;28;25 - 00;47;50;13

And I think that those sorts of subsets of variants also lend themselves to answering these questions about interactions between genes and interactions between variants and then being able to model what's actually happening in us, eventually. And which is totally required, except for in the case where you have like such clear clinical cases, really simple monogenic diseases,

00;47;50;13 - 00;48;13;06

but I don't think we should be satisfied as a field with monogenic diseases. I think we're going to run out of juice if we do that and have less fun.

Ziyi: Amazing. It's so nice to see the efforts scientists like yourself put into the field of variant interpretation and hopefully get to our goal of an atlas of variant affects, but will it happen in the next ten years?

00;48;13;09 - 00;48;36;02

Do our specialists think we'll have a map for every gene by 2035?

Willow Coyote-Maestas: I can argue that we already have a map for every gene. We already have AlphaMissense, and it does a reasonable job in most cases, I would say we're already there.

I'd say 10 to 20 years from now, we'll almost certainly have something that tells you this is what a variant does, because I think we already have that.

00;48;36;07 - 00;48;56;01

My hope is that I can, like, twist people's arms and encourage them enough that they should be thinking about mechanism a bit more. Is this going to have an effect beyond these simple variants in simple cases? And I think that's really dependent on how much we dream and whether we're strategic about how we go about the approaches that we're doing.

00;48;56;01 - 00;49;19;16

But what I think really matters is the so what. So you now know this variant, it's causing a problem. We want to go to the next step, which is designing therapies, getting a sense of that. We need to understand what's going wrong. And we need to start connecting more to the drug discovery side of things. That to me is the really next big thing to start to think about from the clinical side, beyond the like, how do we understand the complex context?

00;49;19;16 - 00;49;49;21

But then how do we actively inform drug discovery? So like, let's say we have this model for biogenesis, right? And I can tell you, for every variant, how much it's altering protein and then how that's happening, that could develop, you know, give you hypotheses about where you might want to target a chaperone to rescue. And then maybe we can do guided drug discovery campaigns using docking or something, saying like, target this one part of a protein. That's, to me, the future, at least from a translational perspective.

00;49;49;24 - 00;50;15;17

Ziyi: How about your perspective, Dr. Glazer?

Andrew Glazer: Yeah, I think it's a really exciting time to be a MAVE researcher. And there's lots of exciting advances in a couple of different areas. So I think one of the areas is just thinking about scale. So as a field, I think over the past decade, if you looked at what's been published and what's being used, we have a few genes that we have really nice MAVE datasets for.

00;50;15;20 - 00;50;46;15

But if you look at the whole genome, 20,000 or so genes, we really haven't done MAVE experiments for the vast majority of genes in the genome. So I think thinking about over the next few years, how do we actually scale up, where it might take in the past, 5 or 6 years of extensive work to do one single gene, how do we scale that up to we can iterate a little faster and scale up to do lots of different genes at the same time, and maybe even start approaching a majority of all the 20,000 genes in the genome.

00;50;46;18 - 00;51;09;09

I think there's lots of really exciting work in also developing new detailed assays and cell systems that assay a key function of a gene. So one idea, for example, is, maybe if you're studying a heart gene, maybe you don't actually want to study it in a non-heart cell line, like a kidney cell line like what we're using.

00;51;09;11 - 00;51;30;09

Maybe you actually want to start to study it in a heart cell. So there's ways that we can take induced pluripotent stem cells and differentiate them into actual heart cells beating in a dish. There's some really interesting work mainly led by a couple other different groups for actually introducing pools of variants in these heart cells.

00;51;30;15 - 00;51;52;14

And then you can maybe even actually study all these heart genes in heart cells. And, kind of building complex, cellular systems that are studying genes in the correct context with the correct binding partners, maybe even in the correct tissue. You really get a more precise measurement of how these genes are working.

00;51;52;16 - 00;52;15;17

Adrine: So, more tissue-specific variant effects? But how will that be translated to clinical care?

Andrew: I mean, I think it's a really exciting time to be a geneticist, because we're essentially doing a giant genetics experiment on the human population right now. So every year we're sequencing hundreds of thousands, if not millions, of people all over the world. And those numbers are growing.

00;52;15;19 - 00;52;36;00

And if you think about the cost to sequence a genome, it's probably a couple hundred bucks now. And, you know, with the exception of cancer or somatic mutations, your genome doesn't really change. You don't need to get a new genome sequenced every year to see if it changed. And so it starts to actually be pretty efficient to generate these genome sequences for large fractions of the population.

00;52;36;03 - 00;53;02;03

And so we're basically finding tons and tons of mutations. And I think the MAVE field is perfectly positioned to really help interpret those mutations. And so, I think if you look at the current model, we really have a reactive model where a patient will get sequenced and they will find a mutation and then some lab that studies that type of gene will maybe write a grant, maybe start making a mouse, maybe start generating that mutation.

00;53;02;03 - 00;53;23;20

Maybe a few years from now, we'll have data to say whether that mutation disrupts the function of that protein or not. But I think where I see our field going in a decade is really switching over to a prospective model, where we can actually, will find a new mutation in a patient, and we'll actually be able to look up on a big list from one of these tables, from one of these MAVE experiments.

00;53;23;20 - 00;53;42;03

And we'll actually be able to say, yeah, you know, that mutation has actually been studied a couple of years ago in this high-throughput experiment. And we actually have some indication that that mutation is the likely cause of your disease. Maybe it's not. Maybe it's just a coincidence. And we'll actually be able to nearly instantly be able to provide that type of genetic data to help inform patient care.

00;53;42;03 - 00;54;08;09

And I think the other ideas I was saying is, is really learning about the biology. So by studying these variants in lots of different environmental and genetic contexts, maybe even a therapeutic context, we can really more precisely learn about how these genes are working. And that will feed back into our knowledge about how biology works, how, you know, in the case of ion channels, how these channels are working in the heart or in the brain or in other organs as well.

00;54;08;11 - 00;54;35;24

Alex: Thank you, Dr. Coyote and Dr. Glazer for joining us today. In this episode, we explored how channel proteins and especially functions of ion transporters are intertwined with the biophysics field, with essential functions on brain and heart metabolism. We explored how understanding the biology is essential for the translational application of MAVEs beyond variant interpretation and into the treatment sphere.

00;54;35;27 - 00;55;11;27

Moreover, we saw how understanding the biology can really mean understanding how biological phenomena intersect with the physical world. By taking advantage of tools from measuring physical processes, we can take advantage of human knowledge in different spheres to help design cures for diseases caused by dysfunctions of human membrane proteins. To decipher human proteins, we may therefore need to produce variant effect maps, where the effect is actually how it behaves under different contexts and with different physical measurement tools.

00;55;11;29 - 00;55;47;00

This means that variant effect mapping is really only one of the many steps required for a future of precision medicine. But until then, now is the time for the rapid fire questions.

Moez Dawood: DNA or RNA?

Andrew Glazer: DNA.

Moez: R or Python?

Andrew Glazer. Ooh, I'm going to say R.

Moez: Short read or long read?

Andrew Glazer: I like short read. You get the scale.

Moez: Single-cell or bulk?

Andrew Glazer: Bulk.

Moez: Knock-in or knock-out?

00;55;47;02 - 00;56;18;04

Andrew Glazer: I'm going to say knock-out.

Moez: Golden Gate or Gibson?

Andrew Glazer: I use both, but I would say my first love is Gibson.

Moez: Coding or non-coding?

Andrew Glazer: Coding.

Moez: In vitro or in vivo.

Andrew Glazer: In vitro.

Moez: Favorite model organism?

Andrew Glazer: I studied fish when I was in graduate school, so I would have to say fish, but now it's cell lines. You can do stuff with cell lines that's big scale.

00;56;18;07 - 00;56;47;14

Moez: Favorite scientist?

Andrew Glazer: That's a good one. I would probably say Darwin.

Moez: Favorite media?

Andrew Glazer: HEK media.

Moez: Favorite sequencing technology?

Andrew Glazer: You got to say Illumina. Illumina's revolutionized the world.

Moez: Favorite piece of lab equipment?

00;56;47;17 - 00;56;56;11

Andrew Glazer: Centrifuge.

Moez: Favorite science movie or medium?

00;56;56;13 - 00;57;10;27

Andrew Glazer: Favorite science movie? I love *Contact*.

Moez: Something outside the lab that you wish you could multiplex?

00;57;10;29 - 00;57;39;13

Andrew Glazer: Learning languages.

Moez: What is the stupidest thing you have ever done in the lab?

Andrew Glazer: One time, I was dissolving, I was making a one-liter bottle of formaldehyde solution, and I was heating it up to get the powder into solution. And I kept the cap on the bottle while I was heating it up. And the bottle exploded and poured one liter formaldehyde all over the fume hood.

00;57;39;15 - 00;57;46;25

Moez: Wow. What is the smartest thing you've ever done in the lab?

00;57;46;27 - 00;58;06;07

Andrew Glazer: Try to turn my biological question into a sequencing question.